

PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS

UDC 799.1:[378.015.31:502/504

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19609616>

**The role of sport fishing in shaping environmental awareness among youth
and developing a culture of responsible fishing**

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Accepted: 13.12.2025 | Published: 30.12.2025

***Abstract.** The relevance of the study is determined by the need to strengthen the educational potential of sport amid escalating environmental challenges, increasing anthropogenic pressure on natural ecosystems, and the need to foster a responsible attitude toward the natural environment among young people. In this regard, particular importance is attached to sporting activities that combine physical activity, compliance with regulatory requirements, and direct human interaction with nature. One such activity is sport fishing, which possesses not only a competitive dimension but also a pronounced educational, ecological, and value-oriented potential. The **purpose of the article** is to provide a theoretical substantiation of the role of sport fishing in shaping environmental awareness among youth and in developing a culture of responsible fishing. **Methods.** To achieve this purpose, a set of theoretical research methods was employed, including analysis and synthesis of scholarly literature, comparison, generalization, systematization, terminological analysis, and structural-functional analysis. **Results.** The study found that environmental awareness among youth is a complex integrative construct encompassing cognitive, value-motivational, emotional-*

*personal, and behavioral components. It is substantiated that sport fishing effectively shapes environmental awareness among young people, as it combines sports training, self-discipline, self-control, compliance with rules, and the practical assimilation of norms of responsible behavior in the natural environment. It is demonstrated that direct interaction with aquatic ecosystems, participation in training sessions and competitions, adherence to sports ethics, and compliance with established regulations create favorable conditions for transforming environmental knowledge into stable patterns of environmentally appropriate behavior. It is determined that important outcomes of such activity include the development in young people of an attentive attitude toward the condition of water bodies, an awareness of the value of aquatic biological resources, a willingness to comply with established rules, and the ability to align their actions with environmental appropriateness. It is established that the educational potential of sport fishing is realized through personal experience of interaction with nature, the norm-governed character of sporting activity, ethical self-regulation, and the assimilation of environmental values. It is **concluded** that sport fishing has considerable educational potential and can be regarded as an effective means of engaging young people in environmentally responsible interaction with the natural environment. Prospects for further research lie in developing pedagogical conditions and practical models for the use of sport fishing in environmental education for youth.*

Keywords: *aquatic biological resources, aquatic ecosystems, environmental management, value orientations, self-regulation, environmentally responsible behavior.*

Роль риболовного спорту у формуванні екологічної свідомості молоді та розвитку культури відповідального лову

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***Анотація.** Актуальність дослідження зумовлена необхідністю посилення виховних можливостей спорту в умовах загострення екологічних викликів, зростання антропогенного навантаження на природні екосистеми та потреби формування у молоді відповідального ставлення до природного середовища. Особливого значення в цьому контексті набувають види спортивної діяльності, що поєднують рухову активність, дотримання нормативних вимог і безпосередню взаємодію людини з природою. Одним із таких видів є риболовний спорт, який має не лише змагальний, а й виражений виховний та еколого-ціннісний потенціал. **Метою статті** є теоретичне обґрунтування ролі риболовного спорту у формуванні екологічної свідомості молоді та розвитку культури відповідального лову. **Методи.** Для досягнення поставленої мети використано комплекс теоретичних методів дослідження, зокрема аналіз і синтез наукової літератури, порівняння, узагальнення, систематизацію, термінологічний і структурно-функціональний аналіз. **У результаті дослідження** з'ясовано, що екологічна свідомість молоді є складним інтегративним утворенням, яке охоплює когнітивний, ціннісно-мотиваційний, емоційно-особистісний і поведінково-діяльнісний компоненти. Обґрунтовано, що риболовний спорт є дієвим чинником формування екологічної свідомості молоді, оскільки поєднує спортивну підготовку, самодисципліну, самоконтроль, дотримання правил і практичне засвоєння норм відповідальної поведінки в природному середовищі. Доведено, що безпосередня взаємодія з водними екосистемами, участь у тренуваннях і*

змаганнях, дотримання спортивної етики та регламентованих вимог створюють сприятливі умови для переходу екологічних знань у стійкі моделі екологічно доцільної поведінки. Визначено, що важливими результатами такої діяльності є розвиток у молоді усвідомлення цінності водних біоресурсів, готовності дотримуватися встановлених правил і здатності співвідносити власні дії з вимогами екологічної доцільності. Установлено, що виховний потенціал риболовного спорту реалізується через особистісний досвід взаємодії з природою, нормативність спортивної діяльності, етичну саморегуляцію та засвоєння природоохоронних цінностей. **Висновок.** Риболовний спорт має значний виховний потенціал і може розглядатися як ефективний засіб залучення молоді до екологічно відповідальної взаємодії з природним середовищем. Перспективи подальших досліджень убачаються в розробленні педагогічних умов і практичних моделей використання риболовного спорту в екологічному вихованні молоді.

Ключові слова: водні біоресурси, водні екосистеми, природокористування, ціннісні орієнтації, саморегуляція, екологічно відповідальна поведінка.

Problem statement. Modern sport performs not only a competitive and health-improving function, but also an important educational function, influencing the formation of worldviews, value orientations, behavioral models and socially significant qualities in young people. In this context, types of sports activities that combine physical activity with direct human interaction with the natural environment are particularly important. Such types include fishing, which not only develops specialized skills and abilities but also fosters awareness of the value of aquatic bioresources, promotes an environmentally responsible attitude, and fosters the assimilation of norms of careful behavior in the natural environment.

The relevance of the problem of forming environmental awareness of young people at the present stage is due to the aggravation of challenges in the field of

environmental protection, the growth of anthropogenic impact on natural ecosystems, the deterioration of the state of water resources and the need to establish responsible models of nature use in society. Under such conditions, it is especially important not only for young people to acquire knowledge about nature conservation, but also to develop the ability to put it into practice. However, in practice, environmental awareness does not always ensure a responsible attitude towards the environment. Often, awareness of the need to preserve the natural environment remains only at the level of awareness and does not translate into stable value orientations, self-control, or a willingness to adhere to environmentally appropriate norms of behavior.

No less important is the development of a culture of responsible fishing, since the use of aquatic biological resources requires regulatory regulation and internal acceptance of ethical and environmental norms. In this regard, the formation of a caring attitude among young people toward the natural environment cannot be reduced to mere information or formal familiarization with the rules. It requires such means of educational influence that combine knowledge, practical activity, conscious attitude and direct experience of interaction with nature.

In this regard, fishing has significant educational potential, as it combines sports training, adherence to clear rules and ethical norms, and direct contact with aquatic ecosystems. Its peculiarity is that the educational impact is implemented not in the abstract, but in the real practice of sports activities. Participation in training and competitions, adherence to regulations, norms of sports ethics and rules for handling aquatic bioresources form in young people not only sports behavior skills, but also an awareness of the limits of permissible impact on the natural environment. It is under such conditions that environmental knowledge acquires practical content, and a responsible attitude towards nature is consolidated through personal experience, self-discipline and control of one's own actions.

Analysis of recent studies and publications. In modern scientific literature, certain aspects of the problem of fishing, environmental awareness among youth and

responsible nature management have already become the subject of scientific consideration, but they are mostly analyzed incomprehensively within the framework of separate research areas. Considerable attention of researchers is focused on understanding ecological consciousness as a multicomponent phenomenon, encompassing knowledge about the environment, a value attitude towards nature and readiness for environmentally appropriate behavior. This approach is traced in the work of N. P. Kulesha and S. V. Tkachuk, where ecological consciousness is presented as an important factor in the formation of a personality during youth [1, p. 61–63]. Close to this approach is the work of V. Moshura, which focuses on the structural components of ecological consciousness and their interconnections in the process of its formation [2, p. 23]. An in-depth disclosure of the psychological mechanisms of this process is presented in the work of V. V. Zelenin and D. D. Otych, who emphasize that ecologically appropriate behavior is determined not only by awareness, but also by emotional experiences, personal meaning and internal acceptance of relevant values [3, p. 2–3].

A significant place in modern scientific research is occupied by works that interpret environmental education in the context of the educational and sports environment. H. P. Hryban emphasizes that environmental education in physical education should be aimed not only at the acquisition of knowledge, but also at the formation of environmental thinking, worldview, ethics and a responsible attitude towards the environment [4, p. 58–59]. N. Ya. Panchyshyn, Ya. O. Bilyk, V. L. Smirnova, and L. Ya. Fedoniuk also emphasizes that environmental education shapes a person by developing value orientations and readiness to act in accordance with environmental norms [5, p. 13–14]. In this regard, the work of R. V. Gakh and co-authors is important for understanding the role of self-regulation in sports, as the authors associate effective sports behavior with the ability to control one's own actions, follow the rules, and maintain discipline [6, p. 1544–1546]. This approach provides grounds for considering fishing a type of activity in which environmentally

responsible behavior also requires self-control, discipline, and internal acceptance of regulatory requirements.

Foreign studies focus on the behavioral and value dimensions of responsible fishing. Y.-Y. Liao and C.-C. Chang demonstrate that specially organized training on the aquatic environment and bioresources increases students' awareness of the role of nature protection and the sustainable use of resources [7]. T. K. Czarkowski and co-authors note that the practice of «catch and release» is conditioned not only by knowledge of the rules, but also by the level of environmental awareness, value orientations and willingness of fishermen to adhere to appropriate behavioral models [8].

The research work of V. H. Skliar, Yu. L. Skliar, O. O. Gudakov, and O. M. Tikhonova focus on the values and features of natural systems, which gives grounds to emphasize the importance of the natural environment as an integral condition for activities related to the use of its resources [9, p. 13]. I. Zubtsova, L. Penkovska, V. Skliar, Iu. Skliar notes the sensitivity of biotic systems to external influences, which underscores the need for a careful attitude toward the environment and a balanced use of natural resources [10, p. 191]. The above provisions are important for revealing the ecological context of fishing and substantiating its role in educating young people.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the general problem. An analysis of the scientific literature shows that researchers highlight organizational, regulatory, environmental and educational aspects related to fishing and human interaction with the natural environment. At the same time, existing works primarily address individual aspects of this issue and do not offer a holistic view of the educational potential of fishing.

It remains insufficiently highlighted that fishing, as an activity that combines sports practice, compliance with rules and interaction with the natural environment, can influence the consolidation of a caring attitude towards the environment in young people, awareness of the value of aquatic biological resources and the

assimilation of norms of balanced nature use. This necessitates further theoretical understanding of the specified problem.

Formulation of the article objective (task statement). The purpose of the article is to theoretically substantiate the role of fishing sport in the formation of environmental awareness of youth and the development of a culture of responsible fishing.

To achieve the goal, the following tasks were set:

- to clarify the essence of fishing sport as a specific type of sporting activity;
- to characterize the main components of the environmental awareness of youth in the context of fishing sport;
- to determine the structural components and factors of the formation of a culture of responsible fishing.

To solve the set tasks, a complex of theoretical research methods was used, in particular, the analysis of scientific literature, comparison, generalization and systematization, which provided a theoretical justification of the main aspects of the problem under study.

Presentation of the main research material. Fishing sport should be considered as a type of sporting activity that combines competitiveness, compliance with established rules, direct interaction with the natural environment and a pronounced educational potential [11, p. 6–8]. Its specificity lies in the fact that the sports result is determined not only by the technical preparedness of the participants, but also by their discipline, self-control, compliance with regulatory requirements and the ability to act in accordance with the ethical principles of sports activity. Under such conditions, fishing sport appears not just a form of sports self-realization for young people, but also an important means of education, in which a careful attitude to the natural environment is consolidated, and the foundations of environmentally responsible behavior are laid.

Fishing sport occupies a special place among sports activities related to the natural environment, as it combines technical-tactical and competitive elements with

direct interaction between the individual and aquatic ecosystems [12, p. 159–161]. If in many other sports the natural environment primarily serves as an external space for the execution of motor activity, then in sport fishing it is a meaningful component of the activity itself. That is why the success of an athlete is determined not only by specialized training, but also by the ability to act in accordance with natural conditions, the characteristics of the reservoir, seasonal changes and the rules of the fishing organization. In this context, fishing sports become important as a means of educating a careful attitude towards nature through personal experience. Its educational value lies in the fact that young people are involved in activities whose results are directly related to discipline, self-control, attentiveness to the natural environment, and compliance with established norms. It is this specificity that distinguishes fishing sports from many other sports, in which the environmental component is less direct and significant.

It is important to consider that fishing contributes to practical knowledge of the environment. In the process of training and competitions, young people learn not only the rules of sports behavior but also gain experience in observing the condition of water bodies, changes in natural conditions, the characteristics of aquatic bioresources, and the consequences of human influence on the natural environment. Such experience has important pedagogical significance, as it transfers knowledge about the environment from an abstract-theoretical level to the sphere of personally experienced and practically learned [2, p. 23]. That is why fishing can be considered an activity in which a caring attitude towards nature is formed in the unity of knowledge, values, attitudes and behavior. It is no less important that fishing contributes to the development of responsibility in young people, not only for their own results, but also for the method of achieving them. In a sports environment, honesty, compliance with regulations, respect for opponents, self-discipline, and the ability to manage one's own actions are fundamental. In combination with the environmental content of fishing, these qualities extend to the attitude towards the environment. As a result, appropriate behavior is formed at the intersection of sports

ethics and environmental expediency, which significantly enhances the educational potential of this type of activity [6, p. 1544–1546].

Another important feature of fishing is the combination of individual experience with social assimilation of norms. Young people enter a sports environment where certain rules, values and models of behavior are already in place, supported by coaches, judges, mentors and participants in the competition. Therefore, a careful attitude towards the natural environment is established not only through personal choice, but also through involvement in a community where norms and a culture of interaction with the environment are integral to sports practice.

The above-mentioned features of fishing provide the basis for the development of ecological consciousness among young people, which is manifested in knowledge, value orientations and appropriate behavior towards the natural environment [1, p. 61–63].

Ecological consciousness of young people in the context of fishing is manifested through a combination of several interrelated components. First of all, it is about acquiring knowledge of aquatic ecosystems, aquatic bioresources, rules of behavior on water bodies, and the requirements for sports activities. No less important are value orientations associated with the awareness of nature as a significant personal and social value. An emotional attitude towards the natural environment plays a significant role, and this attitude is strengthened by direct contact with it. These components acquire their final practical meaning in real actions, when young people follow the rules, demonstrate self-control, discipline and the ability to correlate their own behavior with the requirements of environmental expediency [3, p. 2–3].

In this regard, fishing has significant educational potential, as it provides a transition from knowledge acquisition to its practical application. Young people not only gain an understanding of the importance of the natural environment and the need for a careful attitude towards aquatic bioresources, but also learn to correlate their sports interests with the requirements of proper behavior during training and

competitive activities. As a result, sustainable ways of interacting with the natural environment are consolidated, in which the desire for a sporting result is consistent with regulatory, ethical and environmental requirements. Such an approach is important for the education of young people, as it contributes to the development not only of specialized skills but also of responsibility, self-discipline, self-control, and readiness to act in accordance with accepted norms. One result of such influence is the development of a culture of responsible fishing. It is advisable to interpret it as an integral characteristic of a person, combining knowledge, values, norms and practical actions aimed at a careful attitude towards aquatic bioresources and the natural environment in general. It is not reduced to formal compliance with the rules, as it encompasses internal acceptance of ethical and environmental requirements, the ability to self-control, and the willingness to align one's actions with the principles of balanced nature management [13, p. 1048–1051]. In this sense, the culture of responsible fishing is a component of the broader environmental culture of the individual and manifests in young people's actual behavior during fishing.

The culture of responsible fishing has several dimensions. One of them concerns knowledge and compliance with established rules, restrictions and requirements for behavior on water bodies. Another is manifested in the internal acceptance of respect for nature, awareness of the value of aquatic biological resources and preservation of the environment as a significant norm. A separate place is occupied by the practical manifestation of these attitudes in the athlete's real actions. No less important is the personal plane, which encompasses responsibility, self-discipline, and a willingness to adhere to the principles of responsible fishing regardless of external controls. Taken together, these features allow considering the culture of responsible fishing not as a random behavioral reaction, but as a stable characteristic of the individual. The formation of such a culture in the youth environment is not reduced to a single factor, but is ensured by a combination of several conditions. First of all, we are talking about the educational aspect, which involves acquiring knowledge of aquatic ecosystems, aquatic bioresources and the

rules of fishing. No less significant is the educational influence, within which an appropriate attitude towards nature acquires personal content. An important role is played by the organization of the sports activity itself, built on rules, requirements and control, which establish proper behavior as a mandatory standard [5, p. 13–14]. Direct experience of interacting with the natural environment during training and competitions remains essential. Of particular importance is the influence of coaches, mentors, judges and the sports team, through which young people acquire the values and behavioral models adopted in the sports environment. Thus, the formation of a culture of responsible fishing is ensured by the simultaneous action of educational, upbringing, organizational, practical and social conditions.

The practical implementation of the outlined provisions can be traced in the examples of modern educational initiatives, within which fishing is combined with familiarizing children and young people with the natural environment and the principles of water resource conservation [4, p. 58–59] The organization of training sessions, accompanied trips and practical master classes shows that this form of work can be an effective means of combining physical activity, knowledge of the environment and mastering the norms of careful interaction with nature. The application of the «catch and release» principle additionally emphasizes the possibility of combining interest in fishing with minimizing the impact on fish stocks [14, p. 1565; 15, p. 17]. Such experience reveals the practical dimension of the educational and environmental potential of fishing.

A generalization of the above provisions is a structural model of the role of fishing in fostering environmental awareness among young people and in developing a culture of responsible fishing (fig. 1).

The presented structural model summarizes the main provisions of the study and reflects the logic of the influence of fishing sport on the development of environmental awareness among young people and the cultivation of a culture of responsible fishing. The first block of the model focuses on the characteristics of fishing sport that have a decisive educational value: competitiveness, compliance

with rules, discipline and self-control. They create the conditions under which young people learn to act in accordance with established requirements, to correlate their own actions with rules, and to control their behavior in interaction with the natural environment.

Figure 1

Structural model of the role of fishing in the formation of environmental awareness of young people and the development of a culture of responsible fishing

Source: created by the author

The second block of the model reflects the development of environmental awareness among young people through cognitive, value-motivational, emotional-personal, and behavioral-activity components. The cognitive component is associated with the acquisition of knowledge about aquatic ecosystems, aquatic bioresources, rules of behavior on water bodies and the requirements of fishing sport. The value-motivational component is manifested in awareness of nature as a value and in the willingness to adhere to the norms of a careful attitude toward the environment. The emotional-personal component is strengthened through direct interaction with the natural environment, and the behavioral-activity component is strengthened through practical consolidation of appropriate behavior in training and

competitive activities. Thus, the model shows that fishing creates conditions not only for acquiring knowledge, but also for its transition into real behavior.

The third block of the model concerns the development of a culture of responsible fishing, grounded in knowledge, values, norms and practical actions. Its normative-regulatory component reflects knowledge of the rules of fishing and compliance with established requirements. The ethical-ecological component is manifested in respect for nature and awareness of the value of aquatic biological resources. The behavioral component characterizes young people's actual actions, and the value-personal component comprises responsibility, self-discipline, and a willingness to adhere to the principles of responsible fishing regardless of external control. Thus, the culture of responsible fishing emerges from a combination of educational, cognitive, practical and normative influences.

The general outcome of this interaction is a responsible attitude among young people towards aquatic bioresources. It combines awareness of the value of the natural environment, a willingness to comply with established norms, the ability to self-regulate, and an orientation towards the careful use of natural resources.

Consequently, fishing should be considered not only as a form of sports activity, but also as an important means of educating young people, during which environmental awareness, a culture of responsible fishing, and an appropriate attitude towards aquatic bioresources are formed.

Conclusions. The role of fishing in fostering young people's environmental awareness and in developing a culture of responsible fishing is theoretically substantiated. It is found that fishing is a specific type of sporting activity with a pronounced educational potential, since it combines competitiveness, compliance with rules, self-control and direct interaction with the natural environment. It has been established that, under such conditions, the ecological consciousness of young people is formed through cognitive, value-motivational, emotional-personal, and behavioral-activity components, which ensure the assimilation of knowledge about the environment and the consolidation of value orientations and relevant models of

behavior. It has been determined that the culture of responsible fishing is a stable personal characteristic, encompassing normative-regulatory, ethical-ecological, behavioral and value-personal components and is formed under the influence of educational, organizational, practical and social factors. The theoretical significance of the results lies in deepening the understanding of the educational possibilities of fishing, and the practical significance lies in the potential to apply its insights in working with young people.

Prospects for further research lie in the development of pedagogical conditions and practical models for fostering young people's ecological consciousness through fishing.

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